

UNIVERSITÀ
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UNIVERSITY GUIDELINES ON MANAGEMENT OF RESEARCH DATA AND OTHER OUTCOMES

University of Trento

Approved by the Open Science Commission of the University on 22nd November 2023

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INTRODUCTION

The University of Trento (hereinafter UniTrento) recognizes and promotes the principles of **Open Science** and **responsible research** (transparency, reproducibility of research methods, collaboration, inclusivity, accessibility, rigour, sharing, reuse, etc.) and supports their adoption by its affiliates.

UniTrento acknowledges that all research outcomes, particularly research data, constitute a **cultural and scientific heritage** to be managed, archived, preserved, and made accessible – also in the long term – according to the highest standards of reliability, quality, and integrity for the benefit of the whole society.

Summarizing the current national and local regulatory framework, this document serves as a reference guide for those affiliated with UniTrento to apply for the proper management and openness of data and other outcomes of scientific research, in compliance with current regulations, university policies, and any contracts that may be concluded with third parties.

DEFINITIONS

Research outcome: any tangible product (such as new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, tools, collections of objects, and physical archives of sources and documents) or intangible product (such as data, algorithms, software, workflows, protocols, models, methodologies, collections of documents, interpretations of texts, definitions, statements, demonstrations) created within the scope of a scientific research activity.

Research data: Any information, in any structured or unstructured format (numeric data, textual content, images, videos, sounds, etc.), produced within the scope of a scientific research activity, including validation data for the research results. Depending on the scientific community, this may include, for example, data resulting from observations, survey data, experimental data, data generated by simulations, and data derived from the application of algorithms.

Metadata: Descriptive data of a research outcome, meaning structured information regarding for example, the content, authorship, origin, conditions of use, and any other information that can help with the identification, interpretation, and utilization of the described object.

Affiliated with UniTrento: those engaged in research activities and are authors of research outcomes for or on behalf of UniTrento. This category may include the following, as a non-exhaustive list of examples: professors, researchers, doctoral candidates, collaborators, technical-administrative staff, and students involved in research activities.

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SCOPE OF APPLICATION

These guidelines are consistent with the provisions of the University's Open Science Policy, approved by the Academic Senate on 7th December 2022. They take into account Legislative Decree 200/2021 on the openness of public sector data and the reuse of public sector information, as well as the 'Guidelines containing technical rules for the opening of public sector data and the reuse of public sector information' issued by AGID (Agency for Digital Italy). These guidelines are addressed to all individuals affiliated with UniTrento, especially those participating in projects or other research activities funded with public funds, for which different or additional contractual obligations regarding the openness of data and other research outcomes may be stipulated compared to what is already provided by current regulations. In cases where research is funded by third parties and specific agreements exist regarding the management, access, and preservation of data or other research outcomes, the obligations specified in those agreements are added to the information summarized in these guidelines, in compliance with current regulations.

TITLE I – HANDLING OF RESEARCH OUTCOMES

In accordance with Article 9-bis (research data) of the Legislative Decree 200/2021, it is up to the single affiliate to decide whether and when to open the data and other outcomes of their research, taking into account the University regulations and in compliance with the current regulatory framework on intellectual property, industrial property and personal data protection. This decision should also consider any agreements with third parties (including funding entities; for example, the European Union, within the projects it finances in the framework programs for research and innovation, explicitly requires data publication according to the principles of 'as soon as possible' and 'as open as possible and as closed as necessary'), one's own strategies, the potential impact on society, available resources and possible alternatives such as sharing with a limited number of institutions or research groups with whom collaboration exists, or economic exploitation, also through patent filing.

It is noted, in this regard, that carrying out patent protection procedures does not affect the possibility of subsequently opening the data or other research outcomes once the patent application is finalized. Conversely, making data and other research outcomes available to the public may preclude a subsequent patent filing for the invention they support.

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Regardless of whether research results have been previously protected through patent filing or in any other legal way, individuals affiliated with UniTrento are thus required to handle the results of their research, and data in particular, in accordance with the provisions of Legislative Decree 200/2021 or as indicated in the following articles, when making them public.

Section 1 – Free use

Compatibly with any ethical and legal obligations dictated by current regulations, with particular reference to the protection of personal data, intellectual property, industrial property, as well as the provisions contained in the Statute, the Code of Ethics, and the regulations of UniTrento, and unless otherwise specified by specific agreements for research funding concluded with third parties, the research data for which the affiliate decides to open must be archived and made freely available for both commercial and non-commercial purposes (Article 9-bis of Legislative Decree 200/2021).

Section 2 – Depositing research outcomes

Once they have decided to open their research outcomes, it is recommended that affiliates deposit their results, especially data, in a certified digital archive (referred to as a 'trusted repository') federated with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), such as Zenodo or FigShare. Alternatively, they may deposit them in a disciplinary archive, such as GenBank used in biology to store genetic sequences, or in an archive dedicated to specific formats, such as GitHub for software. The chosen trusted repository should comply with the internationally promoted FAIR principles of accessibility, identifiability, interoperability and reusability (Article 9-bis of Legislative Decree 200/2021). OpenAIRE recommends consulting the FAIRSharing catalogue (<https://fairsharing.org/>) to identify the most suitable archives for one's discipline.

When depositing research results, affiliates are advised to always include in the metadata at least the complete list of authors, the name of UniTrento, and the usage license.

Following these recommendations not only ensures compliance with national regulations but also aligns with the requirements of the European Union's projects funded under framework programs for research and innovation, (for example Horizon Europe).

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Section 3 – Usage License

In accordance with the guidelines of AGID, if there are no third-party rights and if there are no prohibited uses by law, all research outcomes should be made accessible with a license allowing free use that ensures traceability of uses and recognition of the original source. In this regard, where applicable, the adoption of Creative Commons licenses is recommended, particularly the CC-BY license for data and the CC-0 (public domain) license for metadata. To maximize the dissemination and impact of their data, affiliates are encouraged, when possible, to consider adopting the more permissive CC-0 license for data as well.

It is emphasized, in particular, that adopting a CC-BY-NC (non-commercial) license would conflict with the obligations outlined in Article 9-bis of Legislative Decree 200/2021 and detailed in Section 1. For software, it is recommended to use the GNU General Public License (GPL) or similar licenses.

When releasing research data and choosing the most appropriate license, affiliates must pay attention to the licenses of third-party data that may be reused. In case of releasing a collection that includes independent and separate third-party data, the license applies only to the additional part produced by the affiliates in the context of their own research. Each element of the material included in the collection retains its original license, which must be clearly indicated in the collection documentation, along with the source information.

In the case of releasing data that is a remix of third-party data, where it is no longer possible to clearly distinguish between data produced by the affiliate in the context of their research and data produced by others, the license applies to the entire data package. It's important to note that in this case, you cannot include elements in the new package that were released under a CC-BY-ND (no derivative) or more restrictive license. In both cases described above (collection or remix), if the elements included in the new package were released under a CC-BY-SA (share-alike) or more restrictive license, the new package must also be released under the same license. In addition, it is important to note that Italian copyright law (Law Decree 633/1941) stipulates that for all materials—even when already freely available for reading—if the distribution license is not explicitly indicated, it must be assumed that all rights are retained, and (re-)distribution is not permitted without the explicit permission of the copyright holder. The copyright holder should thus be contacted to obtain such permission.

More information on this topic can be found on the creativecommons.org website.

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Section 4 – Storage

Consistently with the interests of any third-party research funders and other stakeholders, and considering confidentiality and security aspects, a minimum storage period of 10 years from the public release of results is recommended.

TITLE II – RESPONSABILITY OF THE AFFILIATES

Section 5 – Data Collection and Management

It is the responsibility of individual affiliates to correctly collect, manage, archive, store, and disseminate their research data and other outcomes, in accordance with current regulations – especially the provisions mentioned in Legislative Decree 200/2021 as previously referenced in Section 1 –, as well as with University regulations, and any funding agreements with third parties.

Section 6 – Data Management Plan

It is strongly recommended for affiliates to draft and keep constantly updated their own Data Management Plan for their research data and other outcomes, even if not formally required by third parties in funding agreements. The development of a plan ensures that data and all research outcomes are managed according to FAIR principles, that the processing methods comply with ethical and legal requirements, and that all necessary measures, including estimated costs in terms of finances and personnel involved, are considered for their proper management, including security measures (e.g. related to confidentiality or storage such as access control and backups).

TITLE III – RESOURCES AND SUPPORT SERVICES AT UNITRENTO

Section 7 – Resources and support structures

The University, through its management structures:

- promotes and organizes training activities on the management of research outcomes;
- provides assistance for projecting and writing the data management plans;
- promotes the acquisition and efficient and sustainable administration of hardware and software infrastructures for the management, processing and storage of research outcomes (capacitive storage).